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ANALYSIS OF PROTECTION OF WOMEN'S HUMAN RIGHT

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Abstract

This paper examined critically what women's rights are and how they are protected at the international and domestic levels. The paper observed despite the efforts towards protecting the Human Rights of women there are several challenges bedeviling the efforts, despite the fact that women make a lot of contributions to the development of national and global economies, these contributions mostly go unrecognized. We are all entitled to human rights. These include the right to live free from violence and discrimination; to enjoy the highest attainable standard of physical and mental health; to be educated; to own property; to vote; and to earn an equal wage for equal work done. But across the globe many women and girls still face discrimination on the basis of gender. Gender inequality underpins many problems which disproportionately affect women and girls, such as domestic and sexual violence, lower pay, lack of access to education, and inadequate healthcare. In conducting this research, doctrinal approach was adopted. The doctrinal method was used to analyse the various literature at hand. It was through the method that the paper reveals what the literature contained on the areas. Also, the paper recommended a systematic change in handling human rights concerns of women, such as, improvement of general education of women, reviewing of laws with a view to ensuring that they are better catered for through the instrumentality of the law. The paper concluded with the relevance and importance of women in nation building which can be seen in certain key sectors like education, medicine, politics, and health.

Keywords: Women's rights, Human rights, Discrimination, Gender.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Women population comprises almost one half of the world population.¹ Yet women are considered vulnerable and need protection. The violation of Human rights of women can be attributed to sex, societal attribution and gender roles. The role of women in the family and development of communities cannot be overemphasized this is due to their visible contributions in political, economic and social developments; hence there is a need for them to be protected.

The United Nations has a long history of addressing women's human rights and much progress has been made in securing women's rights across the world in recent decades. This can be seen in many international Human rights instruments and declarations geared mainly towards the protection of women. Prior to the adoption of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the Commission on the Status of Women (CSW) was established in 1946² by the Economic and Social Council (ECOSOC) which is an organ of the United Nations.³ The Convention on the Elimination of all Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW),⁴ the Beijing Declaration and Platform of Action (PoA, Beijing),⁵ the Optional Protocol to the CEDAW.⁶ At the regional level also, there are efforts made to protect the Human rights of women. Notably so is the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights⁷ which made relevant provisions on the elimination of discrimination on all grounds, including sex. However, important gaps remain because women still face additional forms of discrimination based on their age, ethnicity, nationality, religion, health status, marital status, education, disability and socioeconomic status, among other grounds. Because of

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¹ <<https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SP.POP.TOTL.FE.ZS>> accessed 11 March 2022

² <[https://www.unwomen.org/en/csw#:~:text=The%20Commission%20on%20the%20Status,II\)%20of%2021%20June%201946](https://www.unwomen.org/en/csw#:~:text=The%20Commission%20on%20the%20Status,II)%20of%2021%20June%201946)> accessed 11 March 2022

³ The other main organs of the United Nations established in 1945 when the United Nations was founded are the General Assembly, the Security Council, the Trusteeship Council, the International Court of Justice and the United Nations Secretariat.

⁴ Adopted in 1979 by the United Nations General Assembly

⁵ Endorsed by the UN/GA in 1995

⁶ Adopted and Opened for signature by the UN/GA Res.54/4 on 6th October 1999.

⁷ Adopted in 1981 in Banjul by the Organization of African Unity.

discrimination faced by women on the basis of gender and sex this paper examined critically what women's rights and how they are protected at the national and international levels. Therefore, in conducting this research, doctrinal approach was adopted. The doctrinal method was used to analyse the various literature at hand. It was through the method that the paper reveals what the literature contained on the areas.

In Nigeria, the relevant Protections for the rights of women are entrenched in the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (As amended). The provisions can be specifically found in chapter four (4) which deals with Fundamental Human Rights and Chapter two (2) which deals with Fundamental Objectives and Directive Principles of State Policy. The Rights provided for under Chapter four (4) are justiciable while those in Chapter two (2) are regarded as non-justiciable. There are also other legislations at Federal and State levels which contribute to the Protection of Human Rights of Women.

This Paper analyses the Protection of Women's Human rights, argues the need for their protection. This is divided into seven parts. The first part provides the introduction, the second part deals with international covenants for the protection of rights of women, the third part examines the regional provisions for the protection of Human rights of Women, the fourth part is about the protection of Women's Human rights under the Nigerian Laws, the fifth part deals with the challenges facing the implementation of those provisions, relevant recommendations are made in the sixth Part and the seventh and final part is the concluding part.

2.0 DEFINITION OF KEYTERMS

i. HUMAN RIGHTS: According to Micheline R. Ishay "Human Rights are rights held by individuals simply because they are part of the Human species. They are rights shared equally by everyone regardless of sex, race, nationality and economic background. They are universal in context. Across the centuries, conflicting political traditions have elaborated different components of human rights and differed over which element had priority"⁸ Human rights are rights inherent to all human beings, regardless of sex, race, ethnicity, language, nationality, religion or any other status. Human rights are inalienable,

⁸Michelin R. Ishay, *The History of Human Rights from Ancient Times to the Globalization Era*. (University of California Press Berkely 2008) 3

these rights include, the right to life and liberty, freedom of opinion and expression, freedom from slavery and torture, the right to work and education, and many more. Everyone is entitled to these rights without discrimination.

ii. WOMEN: A woman is an adult female Human.⁹ The term *woman* may also refer to a girl (a female child or adolescent). The plural women are sometimes used for female humans regardless of age, as in phrases such as "women's right."

iii. PROTECTION: The act of protecting or the state of being protected; preservation from injury or harm.¹⁰

3.0 PROTECTION OF WOMEN'S HUMAN RIGHT UNDER INTERNATIONAL LAWS

After the adoption of the Universal Declaration, the Commission on Human Rights began drafting two human rights treaties, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights. Together with the Universal Declaration, these make up the International Bill of Human Rights.

Both Covenants use the same wording to prohibit discrimination based on, inter alia, *sex* (art. 2)¹¹ as well as to ensure the equal right of men and women to the enjoyment of all rights contained in them (art. 3).¹²

The Commission of the Status of Women was established in 1946, the body is dedicated to promotion of gender equality and empowerment of women. The CSW is instrumental in promoting women's rights, documenting the reality of women's lives throughout the world, and shaping global standards on gender equality and the empowerment of women.¹³ At the Fourth Women Conference of the Commission held in Beijing in September 1995 the Platform for Action was signed.

One of the missions of the Beijing Platform for Action is requiring the "immediate and concerted action by all to create a peaceful, just and humane world based on human rights

⁹ Venes D (2017) Taber's Cyclopedic Medical Dictionary. F.A. Davis. 2539.

¹⁰ <<https://www.dictionary.com/browse/protection>> accessed on 12 March, 2022

¹¹ Article 2 of International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights adopted and opened for signature, ratification and accession by General Assembly resolution 2200A (XXI) of 16 December 1966, entry into force 23 March 1976, in accordance with Article 49.

¹² Article 3

¹³ <[https://www.unwomen.org/en/csw#:~:text=The%20Commission%20on%20the%20Status,II\)%20of%2021%20June%201946.](https://www.unwomen.org/en/csw#:~:text=The%20Commission%20on%20the%20Status,II)%20of%2021%20June%201946.)> accessed on 12 March, 2022

and fundamental freedoms, including the principle of equality for all people of all ages and from all walks of life, and to this end, recognizes that broad-based and sustained economic growth in the context of sustainable development is necessary to sustain social development and social justice¹⁴". The platform seeks to achieve gender equality and empowerment for women.

The Declaration on the Elimination of Discrimination against Women was adopted by United Nations member states in 1967. It states that discrimination against women is an offence against human dignity and calls on States to "abolish existing laws, customs, regulations and practices which are discriminatory against women, and to establish adequate legal protection for equal rights of men and women".

The Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women was adopted by the General Assembly in 1979. Its preamble explains that, despite the existence of other instruments, women still do not enjoy equal rights with men. The convention stated in its preamble thus "Concerned, however, that despite these various instruments extensive discrimination against women continues to exist".¹⁵

What amounts to discrimination is stated in Article 1 of the convention as :

"Any distinction, exclusion or restriction made on the basis of sex which has the effect or purpose of impairing or nullifying the recognition, enjoyment or exercise by women, irrespective of their marital status, on a basis of equality of men and women, of human rights and fundamental freedoms in the political, economic, social, cultural, civil or any other field".¹⁶

Such discrimination encompasses any difference in treatment on the grounds of sex which;

- a. intentionally or unintentionally disadvantages women,
- b. prevents society as a whole from recognizing women's rights in both the private and the public spheres,

¹⁴Beijing Declaration and Platform for Action 1995.

¹⁵Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women Adopted and opened for signature, ratification and accession by General Assembly resolution 34/180 of 18 December 1979 entry into force 3 September 1981, in accordance with article 27(1)

¹⁶Article 1 CEDAW

- c. prevents women from exercising the human rights and fundamental freedoms to which they are entitled.

As a matter of fact, traditional attitudes viewing women as subordinates to men or as fulfilling stereotyped roles perpetuate widespread of practices involving violence, of which domestic violence and female circumcision are examples.¹⁷

CEDAW therefore specifies the different ways in which State parties are to eliminate discrimination, such as through appropriate legislation prohibiting discrimination, ensuring the legal protection of women's rights, refraining from discriminatory actions, protecting women against discrimination by any person, organization or enterprise, and modifying or abolishing discriminatory legislation, regulations and penal provisions.

The specific obligations of States to eliminate discrimination against women in political, social, economic and cultural fields are laid out in article 7 to 14 of the convention. The Convention covers both civil and political rights (rights to vote, to participate in public life, to acquire, change or retain one's nationality, equality before the law and freedom of movement) and economic, social and cultural rights (rights to education, work, health and financial credit). The Convention also pays specific attention to particular phenomena such as trafficking, to certain groups of women, for instance rural women, and to specific matters where there are special risks to women's full enjoyment of their human rights, for example marriage and the family.

The Declaration on the elimination of violence against women strengthens the implementation of the provisions of CEDAW. The declaration defines violence against women in Article 1 as:

"Any act of gender-based violence that results in, or is likely to result in, physical, sexual or psychological harm or suffering to women, including threats of such acts, coercion or arbitrary deprivation of liberty, whether occurring in public or in private life".¹⁸

¹⁷I.D Akande: Violence Against Women and Protection Under International Human Rights and Domestic Law: Human Rights Review, An International Human Rights Journal Vol.1, No.1, October, 2010, 27.

¹⁸Declaration on the Elimination of Violence against Women Proclaimed by General Assembly resolution 48/104 of 20 December 1993

The above provision recognized that violence against women can be sexual, traditional or psychological which can occur through domestic violence (family) or in the Community (Harassments, trafficking, prostitution). The Declaration therefore, emphasizes that “Women are entitled to the equal enjoyment and protection of all human rights and fundamental freedoms in the political, economic, social, cultural, civil or any other field”¹⁹ and fundamental freedoms.

In other to strengthen the protection of Human Rights of women, the CEDAW Optional Protocol was adopted by the UN General Assembly in 1999. The optional Protocol allows women to have their claims reviewed by the committee where such rights are denied to them by the state. Communications may be submitted by or on behalf of individuals or groups of individuals, under the jurisdiction of a State Party, claiming to be victims of a violation of any of the rights set forth in the Convention by that State Party.²⁰ All communications must be in writing²¹ with the names of the person submitting it.

Before a communication is considered the committee must ensure that all available domestic remedies are exhausted.²² Upon receipt of the communication the committee may request the state to put in place interim measures to avoid possible irreparable damage to the victim or victims of the alleged violation.²³

The committee considers all communications in closed meetings.²⁴ The Committee shall bring any communication submitted to it under the present Protocol confidentially to the attention of the State Party concerned and within six months, the receiving State Party shall submit to the Committee written explanations or statements clarifying the matter and the remedy, if any, that may have been provided by that State Party.²⁵

In *L.C. v. Peru* (Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination Against Women, communication No. 22/2009, views adopted on 17 October 2011) L.C. was a minor girl, victim of sexual abuse, who had attempted suicide when she had found out that she had become

¹⁹Ibid (n12)

²⁰Article 2 Optional Protocol to CEDAW 1999

²¹Ibid (n12)

²²Ibid (n 20)

²³Ibid (n 12)

²⁴Ibid (n 12)

²⁵Ibid (n 12)

pregnant as a result of abuse. She survived but sustained serious injuries, including to her spine, which required urgent surgery. She and her mother requested a legal abortion so that the operation could proceed. This was denied by a hospital, claiming that the victim's life was not in danger. Finally, after 3 months and having miscarried, she had the surgery but she is currently paralyzed from the neck down, having regained only partial movement in the hands. The Committee found a violation of her right to health, since the decision on the abortion had not taken sufficiently into account the damage of the decision on her mental and physical health. Her health would have required access to both the surgery and the therapeutic abortion, especially given the circumstances (her age, the suicide attempt and sexual abuse).

4.0 REGIONAL PROTECTION OF HUMAN RIGHTS OF WOMEN

The main women's Human Rights instruments in Africa are the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (ACHPR) and the Protocol to the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights on the Rights of Women in Africa (Maputo Protocol). The two instruments provide necessary protection to women by prohibiting discrimination and making provisions for equal enjoyment of rights to both men and women.

The African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights contain relevant provisions on the protection of rights of women. Article 2 "Every individual shall be entitled to the enjoyment of the rights and freedoms recognized and guaranteed in the present Charter without distinction of any kind such as race, ethnic group, color, sex, language, religion, political or any other opinion, national and social origin, fortune, birth or other status."²⁶ Using the phrase "every individual" in the article, means that both men and women shall be entitled to enjoyment of their rights and freedom under the charter without distinction of any kind including 'sex'. Article 3 deals with equal protection in the following terms "Every individual shall be equal before the law. Every individual shall be entitled to equal protection of the law".²⁷ The Charter further provided in Article 18 "The State shall ensure the elimination of all discrimination against women and also ensure the protection of the rights of the woman and the child as stipulated in international declarations and conventions." Perhaps this is

²⁶ Article 2 of the African Charter on Human and People's Rights

²⁷ Article 3(1) and (2)

the most direct attempt to ensure the protection of women from discrimination and draws inspiration from international declarations and conventions such as the CEDAW. Unfortunately, the provision does not address the Human Rights of women in Africa because while the Article prohibits discrimination it only does so in family context. More so, there are no explicit provisions guaranteeing the right of consent during and after marriage. These omissions are compounded by the fact that the charter places emphasis on traditional African values and traditions without addressing the fact that many customary practices, such as female genital mutilation, forced marriage and wife inheritance can be harmful... to women.²⁸

The second regional instrument is the Protocol to the ACHPR on the Rights of Women in Africa. It is also known as the Maputo Protocol. The Protocol was adopted by the African Union in Maputo, Mozambique in 2003 in the form of a protocol to the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Right. The Protocol guarantees comprehensive rights to women including rights to Life, Integrity and Security of the Person,²⁹ Access to Justice and Equal Protection before the Law,³⁰ Right to Participation in the Political and Decision-Making Process³¹ Elimination of Discrimination against Women³², Protection of Women in Armed Conflicts³³, among others.

It is worthy of note that the protocol does not provide expressly that the reservations or declarations are not permitted and as such, states would make reservations similar to those made by some African states to CEDAW.

5.0 DOMESTIC PROTECTION OF HUMAN RIGHTS OF WOMEN

Achievement of Protection of Human Rights of Women requires Domestic as well as Regional and International efforts on a concurrent level. In Nigeria, the constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (As Amended) by its section 42 recognizes gender equality and Non-Discrimination as a Human Rights issue.

²⁸ M. Ssenyonjo, *Culture and the Human Rights of Women in Africa: Between Light and Shadow* (Cambridge University Press. 2007) 44.

²⁹ Article 4 of the Protocol to the ACHPR on the Rights of Women

³⁰ Article 8

³¹ Article 9

³² Article 2

³³ Article 11

There are other provisions of the Constitution which are relevant to the enjoyment of other Human Rights including Right to life, liberty and security of persons and the right to be free from inhuman and degrading treatment³⁴. These rights can also be found under relevant international instruments such as the CEDAW.

Under chapter II of the 1999 constitution provisions are made which are similar to those under ICESCR. These Rights include Political, social, Economic, Cultural and Educational Rights or otherwise termed as “objectives”. The Rights under this category however are not enforceable as they are Non-Justiciable Rights.

There are also other relevant legislations which are committed to the Protection of Human Rights of Women. Notable among them is the Trafficking in Persons (Prohibition) Act 2003. The Act established the National Agency for Prohibition of Traffic in Persons (NAPTIP) with the official mandate to counter trafficking and prosecute traffickers. The agency is also mandated to protect trafficking victims which are mostly women of the One Thousand and Ninety Nine (1,099) victims rescued by NAPTIP, Nine Hundred and Thirty Two (932) are women in 2018.³⁵ Offences relating to women under the Act can be seen in offences relating to prostitution and sexual exploitation of Children and Offences relating to prostitution and forced prostitution. The Act also provides for punishments ranging from 12 Months for attempting to commit trafficking to 10 years for procuring or organizing foreign travels for the purpose of prostitution.³⁶

The enactment of the VAPP Act, which contains extensive provisions on different aspects of violence, including violence against women, are hence a crucial development with the potential, arguably, to protect and promote the Human Rights of Women in Nigeria. It is a consolidation of different bills, “which sought to abolish all obsolete laws relating to matters such as rape and assault, and enact new laws on hitherto neglected areas such as domestic violence”.³⁷ The Act in Section 6(1) provides that the circumcision or genital

³⁴ Chapter IV of the 1999 Constitution.

³⁵NAPTIP Research and Program Development Department Data 2018 found at <https://www.naptip.gov.ng/about-naptip-2/data-analysis-report/> accessed on 15 March 2022

³⁶Section 15 and 16 of the Trafficking in Persons (Prohibition) Act 2003.

³⁷C. Onyemelukwe, Legislating on Violence Against Women: A Critical Analysis of Nigeria’s Recent Violence Against Persons (Prohibition) Act, 2015, *in* 5(2) *DePaul Journal of Women, Gender and the Law* (2016) 1.

mutilation of a girl child or woman is hereby prohibited.³⁸ This provision is imperative as it is submitted that Nigeria due to its large population, has the highest absolute number of female genital mutilation worldwide accounting for about one-quarter of the estimated 115-130 million circumcised women in the world.³⁹ This is very good development considering the rate at which Female Genital Mutilation is carried out despite the physical, mental and psychological effect it has on the victim. Another important innovation in the Act was the prohibition of the forceful eviction of a spouse from his/her home or refusing access of such spouse. The penalty is an imprisonment term of not exceeding 2 years or a fine not exceeding N300, 000 or both.⁴⁰ In a bid to forestall harmful widowhood practices, the Act provides that:

“A person who subjects a widow to harmful traditional practices and is liable on conviction to a term of imprisonment not exceeding 2 years or to a fine not exceeding N500, 000 or both”.⁴¹

The VAPP Act the law is a positive step in curbing issues of domestic violence and providing for protection of Human Rights.

Recently, the Nigerian Supreme Court has been at the forefront of holding that discriminatory practices and laws against women are illegal and unconstitutional. In *Onyibor Anekwe and Anor v. Mrs Maria Nweke*,⁴² the issue in the case was a ‘purported disinheritance of a widow for not having a male child.’ Here, a major issue in the case was whether the custom of the Awka people (in Anambra state) which denied a woman of her rights to her deceased husband or father’s property is repugnant to natural justice, equity and good conscience. The Supreme Court per Justice Ngwuta (As he then was) stated, thus:

³⁸ Section 6 of the Violence Against Persons (Prohibition) Act 2015.

³⁹T. C. Okeke, U. S. B. Anyaehie and C. C. K. Ezenyeaku, 'An Overview of Female Genital Mutilation in Nigeria', [2012] *Annals of Medical and Health Sciences Research*, <https://scholar.google.com/scholar?q=www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov+pmc+articles+PMC&hl=en&as_sdt=0&as_vis=1&oi=scholar> accessed 13 March, 2022

⁴⁰S. 9 (1). An attempt, aiding, abetting, assisting or procuring the services of another attracts an imprisonment term not exceeding 1 year and a fine not exceeding N 100, 000 or both as provided in S. 9 (2), (3) and (4).

⁴¹VAPP Act, S. 15 (1). For an attempt to commit the offence, aiding, abetting, inciting or counseling another to commit the offence is punishable by an imprisonment not exceeding 1 year or to a fine of N200, 000 or both as set out in S. 15(2) and (3). For receiving and assisting another who has committed the offence, criminal liability is for an imprisonment term not exceeding 6 months or to a fine not exceeding N 100, 000 or both as set out in V APP Act, S. 15 (4).

⁴² (2014) All FWLR (Pt 739) 1154.

*"I hasten to add at this point that the custom and practices of Awka people upon which the appellants have relied for their counter claim is hereby out rightly condemned in very strong terms. It is punitive, uncivilized and only intended to protect the selfish perpetration of male dominance which is aimed at suppressing the right of the womenfolk in the given society."*⁴³

A similar decision was reached by the Supreme Court in *Mrs Lois Chituru Ukeje & Anor v. Mrs Gladys Ada Ukeje*.⁴⁴ Here, the court relied on the non-discrimination/equality provisions of the constitution as the basis of its judgment. A major issue in this case was whether the Igbo customary law/practice which deprives children born out of wedlock from sharing the proceeds or benefits of their father's estate is unconstitutional. In a lead judgment by Justice Rhodes-Vivour (which the other Justices also agreed with), the Supreme Court held thus:

No matter the circumstances of the birth of a female child, such a child is entitled to an inheritance from her late father's estate. Consequently, the Igbo customary law which disentitles a female child from partaking, in the sharing of her deceased father's estate is in breach of section 42(1) and (2) of the Constitution, a fundamental rights provision guaranteed to every Nigerian. The said discriminatory customary law is void as it conflicts with section 42(1) and (2) of the Constitution.

6.0 CHALLENGES TOWARDS THE PROTECTION OF HUMAN RIGHTS OF WOMEN IN NIGERIA

Despite the efforts towards protecting the Human Rights of women there are several challenges bedeviling the efforts. For example, Section 42(1) (2) of the constitution expressly promotes gender equality in the country. However, this is circumscribed by Section 42(3) of the constitution which states thus:

"Nothing in subsection (1) of THIS section shall invalidate any law by reason only that the law imposes restrictions with respect to the appointment of any person to any office under the State or as a member of the armed forces of the

⁴³ Suit No. SC. 129/2013 (2014) LPELR – 22697 (SC)

⁴⁴ *Ukeje v. Ukeje* (2014) LPELR – 22724 (SC) Electronic Law Reports.

Federation or member of the Nigeria Police Forces or to an office in the service of a body, corporate established directly by any law in force in Nigeria.”

The above provision aids indirect discrimination against women when it comes to employment into the Nigerian Armed Forces or the Nigerian Police and several government establishments.

Women in Nigeria face violation of their right to life through several issues such as high rate of maternal mortality and morbidity. The rate of maternal mortality is not evenly distributed in Nigeria. In the North, the rate is higher than what is obtainable in the south. The major factor contributing to this challenge is the lack of quality care during pregnancy and delivery.

Another widely spread practice which violates women rights is the Female Genital Mutilation (FGM). It consists of all procedures that involve partial or total removal of the female genitalia or other Injury to the female organ whether for cultural or other non-therapeutic reasons⁴⁵. The practice which is still prevalent within some cultures in Nigeria is extremely dangerous and may lead to death in some circumstances.

There are several widowhood practices under which women are subjected to inhuman and degrading treatments such as shaving their hair, sleeping in the same room as the corpse to prove they were not responsible for the death of the deceased. Women are also denied inheritance rights.⁴⁶ Women make a lot of contributions to the development of national and global economies. However, these contributions mostly go unrecognized. Women’s lack of financial control, access to finances and credit facilities further deepens their poverty. With enough and adequate finances, women will have the confidence to participate more in the democratic process⁴⁷.

In Nigeria, most especially in the North, young women are married off at the early ages.⁴⁸ This in turn denies them the right to education and choice of profession. Considering most

⁴⁵ World Health Organization: Female Genital Mutilation: An overview Geneva; 1998

⁴⁶Ukeje V. Ukeje (Supra)

⁴⁷Aisha, H. Some Fundamental Human Rights Affecting Women in Nigeria: Bayero University Journal of Public Law Vol 2. No 1. June 2010 P. 40

⁴⁸<https://articles.nigeriahealthwatch.com/reclaiming-girlhood-early-marriage-a-challenging-public-health-dilemma-in-nigeria/> accessed 15 March, 2022

have to dropout after the marriage to “take care” of the family. Also, women in some societies are denied the freedom to go out of their homes after marriage. This limits their opportunity to find employment or engage in economic activities that will bring in more income to them.

The Constitution of Nigeria protects the right of women to contest for elections for all positions including the presidency.⁴⁹ In reality however, only few women come out to contest and win elections in Nigeria due to financial impediments, domestic burden, lack of proper political awareness and restriction on Women’s freedom of Movement.⁵⁰

7.0 CONCLUSION

This Paper analyzed the Protection of Human Rights of Women; relevant international and domestic provisions were also analyzed and certain factors that hampered the legal rights and development of women in Nigeria. This is in spite of the existing laws and series of attempts to improve the status of women in Nigeria. The paper also acknowledges the relevance and importance of women in nation building. This can be seen in certain key sectors like education, medicine, politics, health, etc. However, we have admitted in the paper that a lot need to be done in improving the lots of women in Nigeria. It is in view of this those suggestions and recommendations were made with a view of protecting the Human Rights of women. If there is one message that echoes forth from this paper, it is that human rights are women's rights and “women's rights are human rights.”⁵¹

8.0 RECCOMENDATIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In view of the numerous challenges facing the Human Rights of Women the following suggestions/recommendations are made;

1. General education of Nigerian women is desirous. The relevance of this is the fact that from this, the general awareness of their rights would be created. For example, most Nigerian women submit themselves to many important issues that affect them negatively as a result of ignorance of what the law says. To prevent this trend

⁴⁹Section 131: 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (As Amended).

⁵⁰ Ake Modupe and others ‘WOMEN AND POLITICAL MARGINALIZATION IN NIGERIA’ (2019) <<https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/188209386>> accessed 15 March, 2022

⁵¹ Hillary Clinton’s: Remarks while First Lady to the United Nations Fourth World Conference on Women, Plenary Session in Beijing, China: 5 September 1995.

from happening again, it is suggested that moral, religious and western education of the women folk in Nigeria is desirable. By embarking on this, women will be informed of their rights, corresponding duties and their limitations.

2. All the laws which hampered the protection of the legal rights of women should be reviewed with a view ensuring that they are better catered for through the instrumentality of the law. Firstly, Section 42(3) of the Nigerian Constitution should be repealed because it aids in discrimination against women in seeking for employment into the Nigerian Army, Nigerian Police and Other Government establishments. Equally, all international treaties and conventions which have been domesticated in Nigeria should be re-enforced for better performance. The Violence Against Persons (Prohibition) Act 2015 is only domesticated by few states. Concerted efforts must be made to ensure that more states domesticate the Act to cater for the challenges faced by women.
3. Our courts should be proactive in their decisions and judgments. Condemnation of obnoxious customs and traditions should be seen in the judgments being delivered by the courts.

Human Rights are well covered under our laws what is therefore needed is rigorous implementation of the lofty provisions of the laws. The Government must make effort in ensuring the Agencies responsible for the implementation of the laws are carrying out their duties in line with international best practices.